

Aging and renewal events in sporadically modulated systems

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Abstract

We describe a form of *modulation*, namely a dishomogeneous Poisson process whose event rate changes sporadically and randomly in time with a chosen prescription, so as to share many statistical properties with a corresponding non-Poisson renewal process. Using our prescription the correlation function and the waiting time distribution between events are the same. If we study a continuous-time random walk, where the walker has only two possible velocities, randomly established at the times of the events, we show that the two processes also share the same second moment. However, the modulated diffusion process undergoes a dynamical transition between superstatistics and a Lévy walk process, sharing the scaling properties of the renewal process only asymptotically. The *aging* experiment – based on the evaluation of the waiting time for the next event, *given* a certain time distance between another previous event and the beginning of the observation – seems to be the key experiment to discriminate between the two processes.

1. Time series with inverse-power-law waiting times

In this paper we numerically and theoretically discuss the statistical properties of a time series $\{\tau_i\}$ generated from within two different approaches to complexity, *renewal* and *modulation*, in such a way as to produce in both ways the same time distribution density $\psi(\tau)$ asymptotically decaying with an inverse power law. In our numerical treatment we use the simplest form

$$\psi(\tau) = (\mu - 1) \frac{T^{\mu-1}}{(\tau + T)^\mu} \quad (1)$$

with $2 < \mu < 3$. This distribution is properly normalized, and the parameter T , making this normalization possible, gives information on the lapse of time necessary to reach the time asymptotic condition when $\psi(\tau)$ becomes identical to an inverse power law.

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We use the sequence $\{\tau_i\}$ to distribute events on the time axis. The first event occurs at $t = \tau_1$, the second at time $t = \tau_1 + \tau_2$, and so on. The time intervals between two consecutive events are called *laminar regions*, the reason being that the dynamical model here under study to illustrate renewal theory is an idealization of the celebrated Manneville map [1], with the time interval between two events representing the fluid regular state. We keep calling these time intervals laminar regions even when working with modulation.

For the theoretical discussion of this paper, it is useful to turn the sequence of times $\{\tau_i\}$ into a diffusion generating fluctuation $\xi(t)$. Each time laminar region is assigned through a coin tossing procedure either the value W or the value $-W$ ($W > 0$), thus creating a dichotomous fluctuation $\xi(t)$, which is interpreted as a stochastic velocity. We then shall study the time evolution of the coordinate $x(t)$, obeying the dynamic prescription

$$\dot{x} = \xi. \quad (2)$$

The central issue of this study of the two kind of diffusion processes (renewal or modulation) has to do with scaling, namely, the property

$$p(x, t) = \frac{1}{t^\delta} F\left(\frac{x}{t^\delta}\right), \quad (3)$$

which is expected to hold true in the time asymptotic limit. Complexity, namely the departure from ordinary statistical mechanics, is signaled by either $\delta \neq 0.5$ or $F(y)$ departing from the Gaussian form, or by both properties.

2. Modulation vs. renewal

The modulation approach to complexity, meant as the foundation of non-exponential waiting time distributions, is based on conventional Poisson processes whose rates sporadically changes in time (dishomogenous processes). For instance, a double-well potential under the influence of white noise yields the exponential distribution of the time of sojourn in the two wells [2]. In the case of a symmetric double-well potential we have

$$\psi_\lambda(\tau) = \lambda \exp(-\lambda\tau). \quad (4)$$

The parameter λ is determined by the Arrhenius formula $\lambda = k \exp[-Q/k_B\theta]$. In the case when either the barrier intensity Q [2] or temperature θ [3] are slowly modulated, the resulting waiting time distribution becomes a superposition of infinitely many exponentials. It is known [4] that a superposition of infinitely many exponentially decaying functions can generate an inverse power law. If values of τ_i , with different labels i are selected from different exponential distribution, the resulting process is no doubt renewal. To make it become a form of modulation theory, we have to draw a large sequence of time values, with the index i moving from i_λ to $i = i_\lambda + N_d$, with $N_d \gg 1$, from the same exponential distribution $\psi_\lambda(\tau) = \lambda \exp(-\lambda\tau)$.

In recent times, the term superstatistics has been coined [5] to denote an approach to non-canonical distributions, of any form, not only the Nutting (Tsallis) form, as in the original work of Beck [6]. We note that Cohen points out explicitly [5] that the time scale to change from a canonical distribution to another must be much larger than the time scale of each canonical process. Thus, we can qualify superstatistics as a form of infinitely slow modulation. According to the modulation theory, we write the waiting time distribution $\psi(\tau)$ under the following form:

$$\psi(\tau) = \int d\lambda \Pi(\lambda) \lambda \exp(-\lambda\tau), \quad (5)$$

where $\Pi(\lambda)$ is the Γ distribution of order $\mu - 1$ given by

$$\Pi(\lambda) = \frac{T^{\mu-1}}{\Gamma(\mu-1)} \lambda^{\mu-2} \exp(-\lambda T). \quad (6)$$

This formula was proposed by Beck [6] and used in a later work [7].

After generating the sequence $\{\lambda_j\}$ according to (6), we create the sequence $\{\tau_i\}$ with the following protocol. For any number λ_j , we generate a sequence $\{\tau_i^{(\lambda_j)}\}$ with a distribution density $\psi_{\lambda_j}(\tau) = \lambda_j \exp(-\lambda_j\tau)$. To realize modulation, we create the sequence $\{\tau_i\} \equiv \{\tau_1^{(\lambda_1)}, \tau_2^{(\lambda_1)}, \dots, \tau_{N_d}^{(\lambda_1)}, \tau_1^{(\lambda_2)}, \tau_2^{(\lambda_2)}, \dots, \tau_{N_d}^{(\lambda_2)}, \dots\}$. This means that after any extraction of λ we draw a fixed number N_d of waiting times. Notice that according to the arguments of Cohen [5] for modulation to be identified with superstatistics, it is necessary to make N_d very large, virtually infinite. This serves the purpose of allowing the system to reach the local form of canonical equilibrium. In the case of this paper the condition of canonical equilibrium is replaced by a form of ordinary diffusion with ordinary scaling. This is the diffusion process generated by Eq. (2).

Our prescription yields for $\psi(\tau)$ the non-exponential form of Eq. (1). We compare the generated modulation process with the corresponding renewal one, namely with the same $\psi(\tau)$. This latter process can be numerically obtained by setting $N_d = 1$, or, simply, by reshuffling the series $\{\tau_i\}$. Notice that the renewal process can also be obtained by directly generating $\psi(\tau)$, without any recourse to Poisson distributions. In other words, the renewal process yields a time series which is homogeneous and non-Poissonian. Since $\mu > 2$, the renewal process is ergodic, and the correlation function of the fluctuation $\xi(t)$, $\langle \xi(t_1)\xi(t_2) \rangle$, with $t_2 > t_1$, can be evaluated by adopting the time average,

$$\langle \xi(t_1)\xi(t_2) \rangle = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_0^T dt \xi(t)\xi(t + t_2 - t_1)}{T}. \quad (7)$$

Using renewal theory [8] we find for the normalized correlation function $\Phi_\xi(t)$

$$\Phi_\xi(t) \equiv \frac{1}{W^2} \langle \xi(t_0)\xi(t_0 + t) \rangle = \frac{1}{W^2} \langle \xi(0)\xi(t) \rangle, \quad (8)$$

the following analytical expression:

$$\Phi_\xi(t) = \frac{1}{\langle \tau \rangle} \int_t^\infty d\tau (\tau - t) \psi(\tau) \rightarrow \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \Phi_\xi(t) = \frac{\psi(t)}{\langle \tau \rangle}, \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \tau \rangle \equiv \int_0^\infty \psi(\tau)\tau d\tau$. On the other hand the distribution density $\Pi(\lambda)$ is an equilibrium distribution allowing us to evaluate the correlation function through the prescription of Eq. (7) even if we realize the inverse power law distribution of Eq. (1) through modulation rather than by means of the renewal prescription. We note that the time spent by the system with a given λ is inversely proportional to λ . Thus, the use of the prescription of Eq. (7) yields for the stationary correlation function, the expressions

$$\Phi_\xi(t) = \frac{\int d\lambda \frac{\Pi(\lambda)}{\lambda} \exp(-\lambda t)}{\int d\lambda \frac{\Pi(\lambda)}{\lambda}}. \quad (10)$$

By integrating Eq. (2), squaring $x(t)$, averaging on the Gibbs ensemble, and exploiting the stationary nature of the correlation function $\langle \xi(t_1)\xi(t_2) \rangle = \langle \xi(0)\xi(t_2 - t_1) \rangle$, we obtain that $\langle x^2(t) \rangle = 2W^2 \int_0^t dt' \int_0^{t'} dt'' \Phi_\xi(t'')$. We conclude that the condition $2 < \mu < 3$ makes our prescription to modulation to generate the same superdiffusion of the corresponding renewal process. As a consequence, studying the second moment of the diffusing variable x , through the average over the distribution $p(x, t)$ of the diffusing process is not sufficient to discriminate between renewal and modulation.

3. Continuous-time random walk approach to diffusion

We now address the problem of diffusion generated by modulation and use the continuous-time random walk to derive the asymptotic scaling properties of the process. The diffusion for the renewal problem has been the object of earlier work [9] to which we refer the interested reader to appreciate the difference between renewal and modulation on this specific issue. Here we limit ourselves to noticing that the *Lévy scaling*, namely $\delta = 1/(\mu - 1)$ and F of Eq. (3) being a symmetric Lévy $(\mu - 1)$ -stable function, is a property of the central part of the spreading distribution, which is limited by ballistic peaks forcing the diffusion process to yield multi-scaling.

We now prove how scaling is driven by the *crucial events*, defined as the change of λ in our modulation prescription. In fact, each new drawing from $\Pi(\lambda)$ of a value λ sets the rule that N_d times τ_i have to be drawn from the same exponential waiting time distribution, $\psi_\lambda(\tau) = \lambda \exp(-\lambda\tau)$. This generates a subsequence that for large N_d is very extended, thereby producing a diffusion process with diffusion coefficient D_λ inversely proportional to λ . This stochastic diffusion rule lasts for a time that is equal to the sum of the N_d times. The concept of event implies unpredictability, a property shared by the random drawing of a given λ , and by the successive N_d random drawings of the times τ_i 's from the distribution of $\psi_\lambda(\tau)$ as well. However, according to our definition only the drawing of λ is *crucial*.

We define as $P(x, t)$ the probability density of moving by a quantity x , either positive or negative, during time t , as an effect of the N_d drawings from the same Poisson distribution. Analogously, with the symbol $P^{(n)}(x, t)$ we denote the probability density that the particle moves by the quantity x , as a result of n crucial events, occurring in such a way as to ensure that the particle moves by the quantity x exactly in a time t . Note that after the occurrence of these n crucial events, the particle is in general located at a distance x' from the origin different from x . With $n + 1$ events the particle might overshoot that position. Thus the particle might make the remaining trip using the value of λ drawn at the last crucial event, occurred at a time $t' < t$. In other words, we calculate $p(x, t)$, *i.e.*, the probability density of finding the particle in position x at time t using the formula

$$p(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dt' \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx' P^{(n)}(x', t') N(x - x', t - t') + N(x, t). \quad (11)$$

Here the quantity $N(x, t)$ denotes the probability density of moving by a quantity x in a time t with no crucial event occurring. The Fourier–Laplace transform of $p(x, t)$, $\hat{p}(k, u)$, is given by the expression

$$\hat{p}(k, u) = \frac{1}{1 - \hat{P}(k, u)} \hat{N}(k, u). \quad (12)$$

This expression is of crucial importance to determine the resulting scaling. To reach this important result we have to define first the function $\psi^{(i)}(x, t)$. This is the probability density of moving by the quantity x in time t , with i time drawings from the same Poisson distribution. This important function reads

$$\psi^{(i)}(x, t) = \int_0^{\infty} d\lambda \psi_{\lambda}^{(i)}(x, t) \Pi(\lambda), \quad (13)$$

where $\psi_{\lambda}^{(i)}(x, t)$ denotes the probability density of moving by x in time t as a result of drawing i numbers from the Poisson distribution corresponding to the same value of the parameter λ . The functions $\psi_{\lambda}^{(i)}(x, t)$ obey the following recursion relation:

$$\psi_{\lambda}^{(i)}(x, t) = \int_0^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx' \psi_{\lambda}^{(i-1)}(x', t') \psi_{\lambda}^{(1)}(x - x', t - t') \quad (14)$$

with

$$\psi_{\lambda}^{(1)}(x, t) \equiv \lambda \exp(-\lambda t) \frac{1}{2} [\delta(x - Wt) + \delta(x + Wt)]. \quad (15)$$

In conclusion, the physical meaning of the function $\psi^{(i)}(x, t)$ of (13) corresponds to adopting the following procedure. With probability density $\Pi(\lambda)$ we draw a given λ . Then, we draw i values of time intervals, and we move the particle by a quantity x with these i drawings.

With these prescriptions we express the quantity $P(x, t) \equiv P^{(1)}(x, t)$ as follows

$$P^{(1)}(x, t) = \psi^{(N_d)}(x, t). \quad (16)$$

In other words, the transition by the quantity x in time t generated by a single crucial event is derived from Eq. (14) with $i = N_d$. Finally, for $N(x, t)$ we have

$$N(x, t) = \int_0^{+\infty} d\lambda \Pi(\lambda) N_{\lambda}(x, t), \quad (17)$$

and

$$N_{\lambda}(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \int_0^t dt' \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx' \psi_{\lambda}^{(i-1)}(x', t') \Psi_{\lambda}(x - x', t - t'), \quad (18)$$

where with $\psi_{\lambda}^{(0)}(x, t)$ we denote the initial condition $\delta(x)\delta(t)$. In (18) there are no crucial events involved because the maximum numbers of time drawings is $N_d - 1$, not enough to generate a new crucial event, if we start at time $t = 0$ with a crucial event. As a result of this partial number of drawings the particle reaches position x' in time t' . The remainder portion of space $x - x'$ in the remainder portion of time $t - t'$ is traveled with no further time drawing, according to the prescription

$$\Psi_{\lambda}(x, t) = \frac{[\delta(x + Wt) + \delta(x - Wt)]}{2} \int_t^{+\infty} dt' e^{-\lambda t'}. \quad (19)$$

To establish the scaling produced by the modulation approach, we have to evaluate the Fourier–Laplace transform of $\psi^{(i)}(x, t)$, $\Psi_{\lambda}(x, t)$ and $P(x, t)$. Using the convolution theorem we have

$$\hat{\psi}^{(i)}(k, u) = \int_0^{+\infty} d\lambda \Pi(\lambda) \left[\frac{\lambda(u + \lambda)}{(u + \lambda)^2 + k^2 W^2} \right]^i \quad (20)$$

and

$$\hat{\Psi}_{\lambda}(k, u) = \frac{(u + \lambda)}{(u + \lambda)^2 + k^2 W^2}. \quad (21)$$

From Eqs. (20) and (16) we derive immediately

$$\hat{P}(k, u) = \int_0^{+\infty} d\lambda \Pi(\lambda) \left[\frac{\lambda(u + \lambda)}{(u + \lambda)^2 + k^2 W^2} \right]^{N_d}. \quad (22)$$

The evaluation of the asymptotic properties, $u \rightarrow 0$ and $k \rightarrow 0$, is essential to assess the system scaling. If we make the assumption of sending u and k to 0 first, and then integrating over λ , we get $\hat{p}(k, u) \approx [u + k^2 W^2 \langle \lambda^{-1} \rangle]^{-1}$ (implying $\delta = 0.5$), where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes an average over an ensemble of Poisson processes, each of them characterized by a fixed value of λ , selected from the distribution $\Pi(\lambda)/\lambda$ and then kept fixed forever. We note, however, that $\mu < 3 \rightarrow \langle \lambda^{-1} \rangle = +\infty$, casting some doubts on the conclusion that $\delta = 0.5$ (superstatistics limit [6]).

We now prove that the scaling stemming from a single modulated trajectory is the same Lévy scaling that is found in renewal processes. In these processes $\hat{p}(k, u)$, according to the Lévy theory [10], is asymptotically $p(k, u) \approx 1 - au - b \cdot k^\alpha$, where a and b are constant numbers. Using (22) we get this asymptotic property provided that we show that $\hat{P}(k, 0) \approx 1 - \text{const} \cdot k^\alpha$. Note that we have to prove that $\alpha = \mu - 1$. For this purpose we focus on Eq. (22), we set $u = 0$, and, for simplicity but without loss of generality, $T = 1$. Substituting $y = \lambda/k$ we obtain

$$\hat{P}(k, 0) = \frac{k^{\mu-1}}{\Gamma(\mu-1)} \int_0^\infty y^{\mu-2} e^{-Tky} \left(\frac{y^2}{y^2+1} \right)^{N_d} dy. \quad (23)$$

At this point, we use the binomial expansion and the useful property:

$$\left(\frac{y^2}{y^2+1} \right)^{N_d} = \frac{y^{2N_d}}{\sum_{i=0}^{N_d} \binom{N_d}{i} y^{2i}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N_d-1} \binom{N_d}{i} y^{2i}}{\sum_{i=0}^{N_d} \binom{N_d}{i} y^{2i}}. \quad (24)$$

Let us plug this expression into the integral, and divide it into two parts

$$\frac{k^{\mu-1}}{\Gamma(\mu-1)} \left[\int_0^\infty y^{\mu-2} e^{-Tky} dy - \int_0^\infty \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N_d-1} \binom{N_d}{i} y^{2i}}{\sum_{i=0}^{N_d} \binom{N_d}{i} y^{2i}} y^{\mu-2} e^{-Tky} dy \right]. \quad (25)$$

The first term gives $\Gamma(\mu-1)/k^{(\mu-1)}$, and therefore the unity term in the zero-th order of $\hat{P}(k, 0)$. Looking at the second term, note that the integrand does not diverge in zero, at the infinity either: the integral can be considered as a Laplace transform (in Tk) of a finite quantity. So, at this first order, we obtain a constant.

In conclusion, for the integral (23) we obtain the expression $1 - \text{const} \cdot k^{\mu-1}$, which is the same first order expansion as for the renewal process, thus yielding $\delta = 1/(\mu-1)$, a property expected to show up asymptotically, whereas the superstatistics scaling $\delta = 0.5$ corresponds to short time scales, where the scenario of a statistical ensemble of never-changing Poisson processes is very accurate.

4. Aging effects in renewal and modulation theories

We have dealt with a number of similarities between two approaches to inverse-power-law relaxation: a dishomogeneous Poisson process and a homogenous renewal one. This distinction is widely made when studying glass-forming liquids. Also the related phenomenon of *aging* has been known for a long time as a property of spin glasses and polymers [11]. The most popular manifestation of aging is given by two time correlation functions, depending on two times t_1 and $t_2 > t_1$ not only through their difference. The decay as a function of $t_2 - t_1$ becomes slower for larger t_1 . Aging is thought to be determined by the fact that the system under study is out of equilibrium and that the regression to equilibrium involves times larger than the observation time [12].

Here we have in mind *renewal aging*. For recent papers on this form of aging we refer the readers to the following few papers [13–15]. The renewal model studied herein yields renewal aging, whose immediate manifestation is revealed by the dependence of $\psi(t)$ on the observation time.

The quantity $\psi(t)dt$ is the probability that a laminar region beginning at $t = 0$ ends in the small interval $[t, t + dt]$. If we have at our disposal a Gibbs ensemble of sequences, all of which begin with the beginning of the first laminar region, located at $t = 0$, to derive experimentally $\psi(t)$ we have to observe the time at which the first laminar region of each sequence of the sample ends. This is equivalent to making *preparation* and *observation* at the same time. Let us imagine

now that preparation is made at time $t = -t_a < 0$. The first measured waiting time is denoted by τ_1 . The first waiting time, at variance with the observation of the successive waiting times, does not necessarily correspond to the total time duration of a laminar region. The resulting histogram records time lengths that are generally smaller than those corresponding to preparing the system at time $t = 0$. Nevertheless, in the case when the waiting time distribution is exponential, both long and short time lengths are reduced by the same percent. Thus, turning the histogram into a normalized waiting distribution density has the effect of recovering the same exponential form. A renewal exponential process does not age. In the non-exponential case delaying the observation process has the effect producing a percent cut of the short-time laminar regions larger than that of the long-time laminar regions. As a consequence, with the normalization of the distribution, the weight of the short-time laminar regions is reduced and the weight of the long-time laminar regions is enhanced, thereby generating a slower decay of the survival probability $\Psi(t)$.

We numerically generated the $\Pi(\lambda)$ distribution and used this approach to generate trajectories, i.e., artificial sequences of random waiting times. We compared the results for the aging analysis of trajectories characterized by the same exponent μ of the power-law, but generated from the renewal process and from modulation processes with different N_d .

Given the sequence of waiting times and an aging time t_a , we compute the difference between each waiting time and t_a . When the waiting time is shorter than t_a , then we take the successive waiting times until their sum exceeds t_a . Then the truncated waiting time is defined as the difference between this sum and t_a . In this way, we obtain a sequence of truncated waiting times characterized by some *aged* probability density distribution $\psi_{t_a}(\tau)$. Aging is revealed if this distribution changes with t_a . As stated, the modulation process with $N_d = 1$ is expected to coincide with the prediction of renewal theory. In Figs. 1 and 2 we compare the renewal and the modulation process with different values of N_d . Rather than measuring the function ψ_{t_a} , we evaluate the *aged* survival probability Ψ_{t_a} , which is related to ψ_{t_a} by the relation

Fig. 1. Left: Comparison between the function Ψ_{t_a} of a renewal process (continuous lines) and the Ψ_{t_a} of a modulation process with $N_d = 1$ (dots) at different values of $t_a = 0, 50, 100, 150, 200$ (from the lower to the upper curves). Right: Comparison between the function Ψ_{t_a} of a renewal process (dashed lines) and the function Ψ_{t_a} of a modulation process with $N_d = 10$ (dots), at different values of $t_a = 50, 100, 150, 200$ (from the lower to the upper curves). The lowest curve represents the brand new function $\Psi(t)$.

Fig. 2. Left: The same as Fig. 1 (right), but with $N_d = 100$. Right: The same as Fig. 1, but with $N_d = 500$.

$$\Psi_{t_a}(\tau) = \int_{\tau}^{\infty} \psi_{t_a}(\tau') d\tau' = 1 - \int_0^{\tau} \psi_{t_a}(\tau') d\tau'. \quad (26)$$

The left portion of Fig. 1 refers to the case $N_d = 1$. In this case, the choice of a given λ determines only one waiting time. As a consequence, any laminar region does not have anything in common with the earlier laminar regions, and modulation is indistinguishable from renewal. The right part of Fig. 1 shows that it is enough to set $N_d = 10$ to make the dotted lines significantly depart from the dashed lines. We see that the dotted lines indicate a faster decay than the dashed lines, which implies that with modulation the aging effect is already significantly reduced. With a further increase of N_d (see Fig. 2) this effect becomes more pronounced. We see, in fact, that the dotted lines tend to overlap with the brand new survival probability. We conclude that for $N_d \rightarrow \infty$ the aging effect is annihilated. We thus conclude that superstatistics, as a form of infinitely slow modulation, yields no aging.

5. Concluding remarks

Let us discuss which are the main results emerging from this paper. First of all, we found that the waiting time distribution is not, by itself, an unambiguous indicator of complexity. This confirms the conclusion of earlier work [16] from within a new perspective made attractive by the modulation, or superstatistics, approach to complexity [5,6]. We have seen that the adoption of the aging experiment bypasses the limits of the conventional methods of analysis, since it establishes beyond any doubt the difference between the renewal and the modulation character of a sequence of times. This is a fact of some physical importance for the physics of blinking quantum dots [17]. The work of Brokmann et al. [18] has already established aging in the intermittent fluorescence of these new materials, and the more recent work of Ref. [19] confirms that this aging is due to the renewal character of the process. Thus, we conclude, in agreement with Ref. [19], that the dynamic process responsible for intermittent fluorescence must be built up on the basis of a renewal perspective. Of course, the fact that superstatistics is ruled out as a proper perspective for the physics of blinking quantum dots does not mean, in any way, that there are no interesting complex processes in nature that might lay their roots on this attractive perspective. This remark is related to the second important result of this paper. Modulation, behind superstatistics, corresponds to a slow physical process whose realization does not rest on a unique procedure. However, it is plausible that any realization of modulation might generate its own crucial events. These crucial events are embedded in a Poisson sea, exerting a camouflage action, which makes it extremely difficult, to reveal their existence. We have seen that these invisible events establish the anomalous scaling of the process. On the basis of the earlier work of Ref. [9] we think that this anomalous scaling refers to the central part of the probability density distribution, and that the resulting anomalous diffusion is multiscaling. There are good reasons to believe that with suitable developments along the lines of the work of Refs. [20,9], it will be possible to address successfully this challenging problem. This is left as a subject of future work.

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